

Hematological Changes in Patients with Chronic Renal Failure Undergoing Hemodialysis – Pre and Post**Purna Chandra Das¹, Debanjan Bhattacharjee², Arijit Majumdar³**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Burdwan Medical College, Bardhaman, West Bengal²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Midnapore Medical College and Hospital, Midnapore, West Bengal³Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Deben Mahata Govt Medical College And Hospital, Purulia, West Bengal

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Renal failure is a situation in which kidney fails to function adequately. There are two forms of renal failure: acute and chronic. End-Stage renal disease is the final stage of chronic renal failure where there is a progressive, irreversible deterioration in renal function which can be substituted by renal replacement therapy, haemodialysis (HD), peritoneal dialysis, or transplantation. During HD, patients' blood comes in direct contact with the non-physiological environment of the dialysis membrane which may elicit a series of changes in the blood cells and in haemostasis.

Material and Methodology: For the present study 62 cases of uraemia were selected attending in Medicine and Nephrology unit outpatient department (OPD)/Indoor ward and from dialysis unit of Burdwan Medical College and Hospital during the period from 1st February 2011 to 31st January 2012.

The methods were selected

1. Hemoglobin Estimation
2. Hemoglobincyanide (HiCN) Method
3. Westergren Method
4. Macro Method (Wintrobe Method):

Results: The present study is a hospital based longitudinal study. This study was conducted with 62 patients, whose specific blood and urinary parameters were measured before and after dialysis. The parameters that were measured here were Total Leucocyte Count (T.L.C.), Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate(E.S.R.), haemoglobin, hematocrit, Mean Corpuscular Volume (M.C.V.), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (M.C.H.), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (M.C.H.C.), Bleeding Time (B.T.), Clotting Time (C.T.), Platelet Count, Prothrombin Time (P.T.), Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (a.P.T.T.), Fasting Blood Sugar(F.B.S.), Post prandial Blood Sugar (P.P.B.S.), serum urea and creatinine, 24 hours urinary protein, serum erythropoietin level, differential count and urine routine analysis with culture sensitivity.

Conclusion: The present study entitled as "Study of hematological changes in patients with chronic renal failure undergoing hemodialysis (pre and post)" is a hospital based longitudinal study. The study was conducted to study the hematological changes in patients before and after dialysis. In doing so, we compared the reports of complete hemogram, coagulation profile and blood biochemistry in patients before and after dialysis.

Keywords: Haemodialysis, Leucocyte Count, Chronic Kidney Disease, Urine For Routine.

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Introduction

Renal failure is a situation in which kidney fails to function adequately. There are two forms of renal failure: acute and chronic. End-Stage renal disease is the final stage of chronic renal failure where there is a progressive, irreversible deterioration in renal function which can be substituted by renal replacement therapy, haemodialysis (HD), peritoneal dialysis, or transplantation. During HD, patients' blood comes in direct contact with the

non-physiological environment of the dialysis membrane which may elicit a series of changes in the blood cells and in haemostasis. Various hematological parameters are changed in renal failure patients before and after HD. Therefore, it is recommended that all patients are screened appropriately before and after dialysis to avoid complications [1].

The world's disease profile is changing, and chronic diseases now account for the majority of global morbidity and mortality, rather than infectious diseases. The causes of chronic kidney diseases reflect this change and diabetes, together with hypertension, is now the major cause of end-stage renal failure worldwide, not only within the developed world, but also increasingly within the emerging world. Diabetes is of epidemic proportions, and its prevalence will double in the next 25 years, particularly in the developing countries. This will place an enormous financial burden on countries, including the cost of the management of end-stage renal failure. Thus, it is medically and economically imperative for awareness, detection, and prevention programs to be introduced across the world, particularly in the developing countries [2].

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is increasingly recognized as a global public health problem. There is now convincing evidence that CKD can be detected using simple laboratory tests, and that treatment can prevent or delay complications of decreased kidney function. Translating these advances to simple and applicable public health measures must be adopted as a goal worldwide. Understanding the relationship between CKD and other chronic diseases is important in developing a public health policy to improve outcomes. The 2004 Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) Controversies Conference on 'Definition and Classification of Chronic Kidney Disease' represented an important endorsement of the Kidney Disease Outcome Quality Initiative definition and classification of CKD by the international community. The 2006 KDIGO Controversies Conference on CKD was convened to consider six major topics: (1) CKD classification, [2] CKD screening and surveillance, [3] public policy for CKD, [4] CVD and CVD risk factors as risk factors for development and progression of CKD, [5] association of CKD with chronic infections, and [6] association of CKD with cancer. This report contains the recommendations from the meeting. It has been reviewed by the conference participants and approved as position statement by the KDIGO Board of Directors. KDIGO will work in collaboration with international and national public health organizations to facilitate implementation of these recommendations [3].

Millions of people around the world suffer from kidney disease and these patients will eventually need a form of renal replacement therapy. Hemodialysis, peritoneal dialysis, and kidney transplantation save lives but the great cost, which are becoming a major issue in western country [4].

Aims

The study is aimed to find out the hematological changes before and after hemodialysis in patients with chronic renal failure.

Objectives

1. To Compare the reports of complete haemogram, coagulation profile and blood biochemistry before and after hemodialysis in patients of CRF.
2. To determine the hematological complications in patients of CRF undergoing hemodialysis.
3. To take precautions before and after dialysis in order to reduce morbidity and mortality from hematological point of view.
4. To assess the changes in hematological profile in chronic renal failure patients undergoing haemodialysis in our institute.

Materials

For the present study 62 cases of uraemia were selected attending in Medicine and Nephrology unit outpatient department (OPD)/Indoor ward and from dialysis unit of Burdwan Medical College and Hospital during the period from 1st February 2011 to 31st January 2012.

Study Population: Patient attending in Medicine and Nephrology OPD/Indoor having CRF undergoing hemodialysis.

Study Period: From February 2011 to January 2012.

Sample Size: Samples obtained during the reference period will be included under study.

Sample Design: Experimental group will be selected after applying the inclusion criteria (patients with CRF undergoing hemodialysis) during the reference study period.

Study Design: Hospital based cross sectional study.

Parameters to be Studied:

1. Measurement of blood for TLC, DLC, ESR and Hb%.
2. Coagulation profile like BT, CT, platelet count, PT and APTT.
3. Blood for sugar-FBS & PPBS, urea, creatinine, sodium, potassium, calcium and phosphate.
4. Urine for routine examination and 24 hrs urine for protein.
5. Blood for hepatitis B & C antigen.
6. Erythropoietin level of blood.

Inclusion Criteria

The criteria for selection of cases of chronic renal failure were as follows (as per criteria stated by Fishberg et. Al, 1939).

1. Blood urea level about 100 mg/dl

2. Insidious onset with signs and symptoms of uraemia such as.
 - Presence of albuminuria, oliguria, pyuria, haematuria, isotheruria with or without oedema.
 - Presence of metabolic acidosis, water and electrolyte imbalance.
 - Presence of hyperkalemia, hyperphosphatemia, hypocalcemia and hyperuricemia.
 - Presence of anaemia and abnormal bleeding tendencies.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with Acute Renal Failure
2. Patients with Acute Glomerulonephritis.

Methods

The following techniques were employed in the Laboratory investigations. The methods were selected from the point of view of their accuracy and simplicity.

1. Haemoglobin: was determined by the cyan-methemoglobin method.
2. WBC: is done by using improved Neubauer's chamber,
3. RBC: is done by using improved Neubauer's chamber,
4. E.S.R.: the erythrocyte sedimentation rate is done using Westergren pipette.
5. Hematocrit (141) was determined by Wintrobe macro hematocrit method.

1. Hemoglobin Estimation

Hemoglobincyanide (HiCN) Method

Principle: Blood is diluted in a solution of potassium ferricyanide and potassium cyanide. The potassium ferricyanide oxidizes hemoglobin to hemoglobin (Hi; methemoglobin), and potassium cyanide provides cyanide ions (CN⁻) to form HiCN, which has a broad absorption maximum at a

Dilution	Optical density	Hb(gm/dl)
1:1	0.13	6.12
1:2	0.10	4.71
1:3	0.08	3.77
1:4	0.07	3.33

Optical Density of Std. = 0.32; Concentration of Std. = 60 mg/dl

2. Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR)

Principle: The ESR is a simple non-specific screening test that indirectly measures the presence of inflammation in the body. It reflects the tendency of red blood cells to settle more rapidly in the face of some disease states, usually because of increases in plasma fibrinogen, immunoglobulins, and other acute- phase reaction proteins. Changes

wavelength to 540 nm. The absorbance of the solution is measured in a spectrophotometer at 540 nm and compared with that of a standard HiCN solution.

Reagent: The diluent is detergent-modified Drabkin reagent

Method: Twenty microliters of blood is added to 5.0 mL of diluents (1:251), mixed well, and allowed to stand at room temperature for at least 3 minutes. The absorbance is measured, against the reagent blank, in the photoelectric colorimeter at 540 nm or with an appropriate filter. A vial of HiCN standard is then opened and the absorbance measured, at room temperature, in the same instrument in a similar fashion. The test sample must be analyzed within a few hours of dilution. The standard must be kept in the dark when not in use and discarded at the end of the day.

$$\text{Hb (g/dL)} = \frac{A_{540} \text{ test sample}}{A_{540} \text{ standard}} \times \frac{\text{Concentration of standard (mg/dL)}}{100\text{mg/g}} \times 251$$

The absorbance of fresh HiCN standard is measured against a reagent blank. Absorbance readings are made of fresh HiCN standard and of dilutions of this standard in the reagent (1 in 2, 1 in 3, and 1 in 4) against a reagent blank. Hb values in grams per deciliter are calculated for each solution by applying the formula. When the absorbance readings are plotted on linear graph paper as the ordinates against Hb concentration as the abscissa, the points should describe a straight line that passes through the origin. An advantage of the HiCN method is that most forms of hemoglobin (Hb, HbO₂, Hi, and HbCO, but not SHb) are measured. e.g.

in red cell shape or numbers may also affect the ESR.

Theoretical Considerations: The RBCs sediment because their density is greater than that of plasma; this is particularly so, when there is an alteration in the distribution of charges on the surface of the RBC (which normally keeps them separate from each other) resulting in their coming together to form large aggregates known as rouleaux.

Rouleaux formation is determined largely by increased levels of plasma fibrinogen and

globulins, and so the ESR reflects mainly changes in the plasma proteins that accompany acute and chronic infections, some tumors and degenerative diseases. In such situations, the ESR values are much greater than 100 mm/hr. ESR denotes merely the presence of tissue damage or disease, but not its severity; it may be used to follow the progress of the diseased state, or monitor the effectiveness of treatment.

Method

When anticoagulated whole blood is allowed to stand in a narrow vertical tube for a period of time, the RBCs – under the influence of gravity – settle out from the plasma. The rate at which they settle is measured as the number of millimeters of clear plasma present at the top of the column after one hour(mm/hr).

There are two main methods used to measure the ESR: the Westergren method and the Wintrobe Method. Each method produces slightly different results. Most laboratories use the Westergren method.

3. Westergren Method

The Westergren method requires collecting 2 ml of venous blood into a tube containing 0.5 ml of sodium citrate. It should be stored no longer than 2 hours at room temperature or 6 hours at 4°C. The blood is drawn into a Westergren tube to the 200 mm mark. The tube is placed in a rack in a strictly vertical position for 1 hour at room temperature, at which time the distance from the lowest point of the surface meniscus to the upper limit of the red cell sediment is measured. The distance of fall of erythrocytes, expressed as millimetres in 1 hour, is the ESR.

Average values in healthy men are: <15mm/hr; in healthy females, they are somewhat higher:

<20mm. The values are slightly higher in old age, in both genders.

4. Hematocrit (Packed Cell Volume)

The hematocrit of a sample of blood is the ratio of the volume of erythrocytes to that of the whole blood. It is expressed either as a percentage (conventional) or as a decimal fraction (SI units).

Method (143)

- (a) Macro method (Wintrobe method)
- (b) Micro hematocrit method
- (c) Electronic method.

5. Macro Method (Wintrobe Method)

Principle: In this method PCV is measured by Wintrobe tube which has a length of 110mm and internal bore of 2.5 mm and graduated from 0-10 cm on both directions.

Procedure:

1. Fill the Wintrobe tube upto mark 10 with well mixed anticoagulated blood (EDTA) by Pasteur pipette free of air bubbles.
2. Centrifugation of the tube at 2000-2300 g for 30 minutes.
3. After centrifugation layers are noted in the Wintrobe tube as under-
 - Uppermost layer of plasma
 - This white layers of platelets.
 - Greyish-pink layer of leucocytes.
 - Lowermost is the layer of RBCs.

Result

The present study is a hospital based longitudinal study. This study was conducted with 62 patients, whose specific blood and urinary parameters were measured before and after dialysis.

Figure 1: Gender Wise Distribution of the Study Population

Table 1: Distribution of Age (In Years) Of The Study Population

Age In Years	Minimum Years	Maximum Years	Mean Age	Standard Deviation
	7.5	75	45.88	17.159

Figure 2: Distribution of Age (In Years) In the Study Population.

Table 2: Table Showing the Comparison of Total Leucocyte Count Of The Subjects Before And After Dialysis.

Subjects	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error mean	Significance (2-Tailed)
TLC	62	8151.6129	3458.64287	439.24808	0.798
	62	8302.4194	3060.18090	388.64336	

Figure 3: The Comparison of Total Leucocyte Count of The Subjects before and after Dialysis.

Table 3: Comparison of Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR) of The Subjects Before And After Dialysis.

Subjects	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Significance (2-Tailed)
ESR	62	83.2903	34.11715	4.33288	0.351
	62	88.9355	33.04040	4.19613	

Figure 4: The Comparison of Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR) of The Subjects Before And After Dialysis.

Figure 4: The Comparison of Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR) of The Subjects Before And After Dialysis.

Subjects		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Significance (2-Tailed)
Hemoglobin	Pre dialysis	62	6.7823	1.42294	0.18071	0.295
	Post dialysis	62	7.0613	1.52771	0.19402	
Hematocrit	Pre dialysis	62	20.6887	4.51344	0.57321	0.394
	Post dialysis	62	21.3984	4.72664	0.60028	

Figure 5: The Comparison of Hemoglobin of the Subjects Before And After Dialysis.

Table 5: Comparison of MCV, MCH and MCHC of the Subjects Before and After Dialysis

Subjects		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error mean	Significance (2-Tailed)
MCV	Pre dialysis	62	87.9598	5.69406	0.72315	0.169
	Post dialysis	62	89.2490	4.63314	0.58841	
MCH	Pre dialysis	62	28.9332	1.92976	0.24508	0.529
	Post dialysis	62	29.1406	1.71869	0.21827	
MCHC	Pre dialysis	62	32.7903	1.42322	0.18075	0.818
	Post dialysis	62	32.7384	1.06263	0.13495	

Figure 6: The Comparison of Hematocrit Values of the Subjects before and After Dialysis.

Table 6: Comparison Bleeding Time (BT) and Clotting Time (CT) Of The Subjects Before And After Dialysis

Subjects		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error mean	Significance (2-Tailed)
BT	Predialysis	62	4.4726	2.56209	0.32539	0.216
	Post dialysis	62	5.0210	2.34655	0.29801	
CT	Pre dialysis	62	4.2839	1.92407	0.24436	0.014*
	Post dialysis	62	5.0855	1.65835	0.21061	

Figure 7: The Comparison of MCV Values of the Subjects before and After Dialysis.

Table 7: Comparison Platelet Count of the Subjects Before and After Dialysis

Subjects		N	Mean	Std. deviation	Std. Error mean	Significance (2-tailed)
Platelet count	Pre dialysis	62	1.6423	0.80125	0.10176	0.058
	Post dialysis	62	1.4074	0.53658	0.06815	

Figure 8: The Comparison of MCH Values of the Subjects before and After Dialysis.

Table 8: Comparison Prothrombin Time (PT) and Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (aPTT) Of The Subjects Before And After Dialysis

Subjects		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error mean	Significance (2-Tailed)
PT	Pre dialysis	62	12.5347	3.14160	0.39898	0.032*
	Post dialysis	62	13.4565	1.15597	0.14681	
PTT	Predialysis	62	28.5758	4.51397	0.57328	0.657
	Post dialysis	62	28.9355	4.48312	0.56936	

Picture 1: Colorimeter

Picture 2: Westergren Sedimentation Pipette With Stand

Picture 3: Pasteur Pipette

Picture 4: Clinical Chemistry Auto Analyzer

Picture 5: Semi Auto Analyzer

Picture 6: Acanthocytes

Picture 7: Iron Deficiency

Picture 8: RBC Cast

Discussion

Renal problems pose a great threat to the present society, with life getting hectic with the passing days. Every year, renal pathologies claim a good many number of lives, thus increasing the mortality rate. Attempts are going on everywhere in the world to bring out newer techniques of treatment, that will lower down the ailing problem of this society, gradually turning into a major life threat. Dialysis is one of the handy techniques in the process of treating renal pathologies. In this study, we aimed at measuring and analysing the major blood and urinary indices before and after the dialysis of a group of selected patients with an intention to find out a solution to this growing problem.

The present study is a hospital based longitudinal study. This study was conducted with 62 patients, whose specific blood and urinary parameters were measured before and after dialysis. The parameters that were measured here were Total Leucocyte Count (T.L.C.), Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (E.S.R.), haemoglobin, hematocrit, Mean

Corpuscular Volume (M.C.V.), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (M.C.H.), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (M.C.H.C.), Bleeding Time (B.T.), Clotting Time (C.T.), Platelet Count, Prothrombin Time (P.T.), Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (a.P.T.T.), Fasting Blood Sugar (F.B.S.), Post Prandial Blood Sugar (P.P.B.S.), serum urea and creatinine, 24 hours urinary protein, serum erythropoietin level, differential count and urine routine analysis with culture sensitivity.

In our recent study, it was seen that out of all the cases collected for analysis, 59.68% were males and the rest 40.32% were females with the mean age for both the groups being 45.88 years as depicted from Figure 1 and 2 and also from Table 1. In the study conducted by Hida and Saito, almost the same results were depicted which states that age distribution differed depending on the primary renal diseases and sex (154). In chronic glomerulonephritis, males were most numerous in the 30-39 year-old group, followed by the 40-49 and 20-29 year-old groups. They decreased with

age. Females showed the same frequencies among the 20-29, 30-39, 40-49, 50-59, 60-69 and 70-79 year-old groups. However, the 50-59 year-old group had the most cases. Among cases of diabetic nephropathy, males were most numerous in the 50-59 year-old group and females in the 60-69 year-old group. Progression of the disease to renal failure seemed to be more rapid in males than in females.

Conclusion

The present study entitled as "Study of hematological changes in patients with chronic renal failure undergoing hemodialysis (pre and post)" is a hospital based longitudinal study. The study was conducted to study the hematological changes in patients before and after dialysis. In doing so, we compared the reports of complete hemogram, coagulation profile and blood biochemistry in patients before and after dialysis. This study also determined the complications that occurred in patients with chronic renal failure undergoing dialysis. The study also aimed to formulate precautions before and after dialysis in order to reduce morbidity and mortality from hematological point of view. More so, the study also revolved around measuring the parameters like urea, creatinine, erythropoietin, 24 hours urinary protein and urine routine examination and culture sensitivity.

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